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Promoting Energy Efficiency Investments in Building Sector: A Stakeholder Consultation Approach

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Energy efficiency (EE) is an integral part of global energy policy, since it is not only widely recognised as an effective means of reducing greenhouse gas emissions, but also ensures long term security of energy supply. Towards this direction, EE investments have a direct effect on reducing energy consumption, while also improving industrial competitiveness and driving economic growth. Nevertheless, despite the demonstrated economic potential and environmental benefits, EE investments are still below policy targets set. In order to successfully identify potential risks and boost the finance of attractive EE project ideas, relevant key actors should be addressed and engaged, while the type of effort and messages to be used for each target group should be analytically examined. The aim of this study is to analyse through a targeted questionnaire the behaviour mainly of project developers, financiers, investors regarding EE investments in buildings, identify relevant risks and evaluate the added value of such investments' implementation. One of the conclusions emerged is that financial and economic risks were rated as the most critical ones affecting the successful financing of EE investments in the building sector.

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